

ENHANCED FILAMENT WINDING SIMULATION FOR IMPROVED STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS OF COMPOSITE PRESSURE VESSELS

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1 Motivation: Composite Pressure Vessels

The technology of Composite Pressure Vessels has evolved for more than 50 years [1]. Applications range from solid rocket motor cases over Liquefied Petrol Gas (LPG) tanks for stowage of heating or cooking fuels to gas tanks for Compressed Natural Gas (CNG) or Compressed Hydrogen (CH₂) in automotive applications. Typical working pressure levels range from 1 MPa to over 70 MPa for the named applications. The vessels may be used stationary or in mobile applications. Technologies include type 3 composite over-wrapped pressure vessels with load carrying metallic liner and type 4 vessels with non-load carrying plastic liner. The demand for these vessels remains high or is rising and new applications are constantly introduced. All these different applications have two common requirements: the pressure vessel should be safe and efficient.

Despite the long history of composite pressure vessels this aim is hindered by the high inherent complexity due to interacting parts, manufacturing technologies and the anisotropic deformation and failure behavior of the composite material used as the principal structural component. The inherent risk of the technology can only be controlled in an efficient manner if the resulting system is well understood.

2 Subject: Structural Analysis

The design of composite pressure vessels is certainly possible in the classical trial and error approach of "build and burst" – as demonstrated by many successful applications. However, this is at least unsatisfactory if not potentially inefficient or in some cases even unsafe. Today's technology requires thorough understanding of its components. For the

example of composite pressure vessels a deep understanding of the systems behavior should be strived for. This can only be achieved by detailed structural analysis. However, this is best used actively as a design tool and not as an afterthought.

Fig. 1. Filament winding simulation in progress

The structural analysis approach should be applicable to all types of composite pressure vessels under all conditions of manufacturing and service. The approach should be useful to optimization and should facilitate frequent design iterations. In industrial practice it is not sufficient if the analysis approach is limited to certain types of vessels or subject to arbitrary restrictions. The approach should give insight in the behavior of the system and should in this way contribute to the confidence in the technology.

Different analysis methods have been and are currently used in the design of composite pressure vessels: Analytical methods based on netting

analysis or classical laminate theory together with membrane or shell theories are frequently proposed [2, 3]. These are valuable tools, but in many cases they suffer from the underlying idealizations that are not realized in practice.

The only currently known method of structural analysis with sufficient generality is the Finite Element Method [4]. Clearly finite element methods are quite ambitious for a multitude of reasons. They may be expensive due to high software cost and necessary in-depth training of the analyst. The use may be very time consuming due to large efforts for model generation, computer run-time and result evaluation and interpretation. All of these reasons are based in history and remain valid today at least in part.

However, specialized tools have always been created to support the tasks of domain-specific analyzes [5, 6]. Such tools can alleviate much of the cited drawbacks of finite element analysis. What still remains is the question of the most adequate modeling: How can the multilayered and multidirectional composite structure be represented in the model in an efficient way, addressing the relevant influence factors from the manufacturing process sufficiently [7].

Fig. 2. Fiber path with start and end points at the tangent line between dome and cylindrical part of the vessel

3 Tool: Filament Winding Simulation

The filament winding simulation was originally conceived to automate the time consuming manual generation of control programs for the filament winder [8]. Furthermore, this software can aid in the design of complete winding patterns (Fig. 1). Usually the filament winding software offers not only interfaces to export control data but also includes some kind of interface to provide data for finite element analysis. However, the applicability of this data is frequently restricted to thin-walled shell models with axisymmetric properties.

One particularly problematic aspect is the accuracy of the calculated thickness build-up. This frequently suffers from strong idealizations and restricts the applicability for multi-layered composite shells and makes the results in the vicinity of the polar opening questionable. The analyst counteracts these effects by manual or semi-manual modification of the data provided by the filament winding simulation. Clearly more advanced tools are highly desirable.

4 Approach: Integrated Software

To aid the "design by analysis" approach of general composite pressure vessels in an industrial setting, an integrated software system is being developed to improve the filament winding simulation with the objective to provide more realistic input-data for the detailed finite element analysis. This software should be able to generate realistic winding patterns as used in the industrial practice, to predict the thickness build-up with sufficient accuracy and to represent the local stacking sequence (layer thickness and fiber angle) at any point of the winding surface. The prediction of properties in the vicinity of the polar opening is of particular interest. The ultimate aim is to provide a complete analysis tool chain to support the iterative design of composite pressure vessels [9].

5 Implementation: Enhanced Filament Winding Simulation

The numerical approach of the proposed enhanced filament winding simulation is to track the fiber band path on the winding surface, to model the fiber band by patches, to accumulate these band patches at sampling points and thus to determine the local thickness and stacking sequence. The resulting data is transferred into a finite element model using layered solid elements [4, 10].

Fig. 3. Meridian section of winding surface

5.1 Tracking of the Fiber Band Path on the Winding Surface

The implementation is based on a grid discretization of the winding surface (Fig. 2). Currently only axisymmetric surfaces can be described by a list of points representing a meridian section of the surface (Fig. 3). However, the general approach is not limited to axisymmetric structures.

In the simplest case of geodetic winding the angle α of the fiber band with respect to the meridian is evaluated at every point with radius r from Clairaut's equation [1, 8]:

$$r \sin(\alpha) = \text{const.}$$

Starting at an arbitrary point with radius r_0 and angle α_0 the progression of points along the fiber band path can be evaluated numerically along the axial coordinate of the vessel. Typically the tangent line, where the end cap is joined to the cylindrical part of the vessel, is used as the starting point. At this point the radius assumes the maximum value corresponding to the nominal diameter of the vessel ($2 \cdot r_0 = D$). The fiber band angle assumes the nominal winding angle α_0 of the layer under consideration. When the angle reaches the limiting value of 90° the turning point is realized and the direction of progression along the axial coordinate is reversed. This point represents the minimum achievable radius. After two direction reversals the axial coordinate of the starting point is again reached (Fig. 2).

The end point of the fiber band path is offset by an angle relative to the starting point. This offset angle depends on the geometry of the winding surface and the nominal winding angle α_0 . In general, continuation of this fiber band path will not result in a closed winding pattern, covering the entire vessel surface without gaps and excessive overlap (Fig. 5). To realize a closed winding pattern, modifications to the computed fiber band path are required. This can be achieved by introduction of small dwell angles at the turning points, by adding a small offset angle between consecutive cycles, by general deviation from Clairaut's equation or by a combination of these methods.

Fig. 4. Overlapping bands (only 3 cycles shown)

Fig. 5. Closed winding pattern
(71 cycles, band width not shown)

Fig. 6. Closed winding pattern
(71 cycles, band width shown)

Fig. 7. Band represented by triangles
(only 3 cycles shown)

In the present implementation small corrective dwell angles are computed automatically to realize a closed winding pattern with approximately 100 % coverage of the winding surface (Fig. 6).

5.2 Modeling the Fiber Band

After computing the fiber band path, the geometry of the fiber band, usually consisting of multiple parallel fiber strands, is modeled: Using the local tangent vector \mathbf{T} to the fiber band path (center of the desired fiber band geometry) and the local normal vector \mathbf{N} of the winding surface the vector of the bi-normal direction \mathbf{B} is computed by the vector cross product.

$$\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{T} \times \mathbf{N}$$

The bounding points \mathbf{R}_1 and \mathbf{R}_2 of the band can be computed using the radius vector \mathbf{R} of the fiber band path and the bi-normal vector \mathbf{B} taking the width w of the fiber band into account.

$$\mathbf{R}_1 = \mathbf{R} + w/2 \mathbf{B}$$

$$\mathbf{R}_2 = \mathbf{R} - w/2 \mathbf{B}$$

The fiber band is finally represented by patches of triangles connecting consecutive bounding points (Fig. 7).

5.3 Accumulation of Data at Sampling Points

The next step is the accumulation of band patches at sampling points to determine the local thickness and laminate stacking sequence. Both winding surface and fiber band are defined in the three dimensional space by Cartesian coordinates (x, y, z) . For the purpose of analysis the defining points of surface and band are projected into a suitable two-dimensional space of surface coordinates (u, v) (Fig. 8).

The method proceeds by considering every patch of the band in turn to find any sampling point contained within the patch. The required check is performed by computing the area coordinates of the sampling point with respect to the triangle representing the band patch (Fig. 9). For every sampling point found, the thickness of the band patch is accumulated to the current thickness at this point. Furthermore the fiber angle of the band patch is recorded in a list representing the local stacking sequence.

Since the number of band patches and sampling points can be quite large, a one-by-one check of

Fig. 8. Surface grid and fiber band in 2D projection

each sampling point for every band patch would result in excessive simulation run-times. Therefore only a reasonably subset of all sampling points is checked for each band patch based on heuristic vicinity considerations.

At the end of this process the total laminate thickness and the laminate stacking sequence is known at all sampling points. In the simplest case, the grid points representing the winding surface are used as the sampling points, but other options are possible (Fig. 10, Fig. 11). The process may be repeated if multiple winding layers should be considered. However, in this case the geometry of the winding surface needs to be updated using the generated thickness data of the previous layer. In general the fiber path also needs to be recomputed.

Fig. 9. Sampling points inside and outside of a given triangle of the fiber band representation

5.4 Transfer of Data into the Finite Element Model

The transfer of the generated laminate data into the finite element model proceeds as follows. In the simplest case, the grid points representing the winding surface are used as nodal points of the finite element discretization. The finite elements may be shell or solid elements. In the case of solid elements the grid points represent the nodes on the inner surface and missing nodes on the outside surface are generated using the normal vectors of the winding surface and the thickness data. The required thickness information for each node is taken from the accumulated band thickness at the nodal points.

Depending on the element type, the internal laminate description may allow for multiple layers with constant thickness and constant angle of principle material direction or for variable thickness layers with variable angle of principle material direction [11, 12]. In the latter case, the thickness and angle data usually have to be input at the nodal points. However, most finite element formulations require that the layers are continuous within the element and thus that the number of layers is the same at all nodes.

It turns out that this may not be the case for the filament wound structure. The easiest solution to this problem is to use a sampling point in the center of the element to record the local laminate stacking

sequence and to use this data to define the laminate corresponding to this element. A more accurate approach may be to use the location of the integration points of the element as the sampling points, e.g. for 4 x 4 in-plane Gauss integration.

In general the finite element discretization is not pre-determined by this scheme but can be adjusted to fit the accuracy to practical needs. It is only necessary to define the location of the desired sampling points on the winding surface and to map these sampling points to the appropriate finite elements.

Fig. 10. Sampling points in 2D projection (only 3 cycles shown)

Fig. 11. Sampling points on winding surface (only 3 cycles shown)

Fig. 12. Band overlap count (only 3 cycles shown)

6 Conclusion: Results and Outlook

The main results of the simulated band deposition on the winding surface are consistent with observations that can also be made with actual vessels manufactured by filament winding. The differences between the real laminate structure and the idealized theory are mainly due to the finite width w of the filament band. They are reduced with decreasing width of the band.

The main observations are:

1. The thickness distribution along the meridian direction is not continuous but stepped due to the band overlap (Fig. 4, Fig. 14, Fig. 15).
2. The thickness at a given meridian position in circumferential direction is not constant but variable, depending on the winding pattern (Fig. 12).
3. The local fiber angle within a layer at a given meridian and circumferential position is not constant in the circumferential direction and is in general not given by Clairaut's equation (Fig. 13, Fig. 14).

In „wet“ filament winding the thickness effects are less obvious due to flow of resin during the winding process. This effect cannot be represented in the present simulation.

The influence of the band width w on the local fiber angle distribution is of particular interest due to the strong directional dependency of stiffness and strength of the unidirectional composite material (Fig. 16). This may have a major influence on the mechanical behavior of the filament wound composite pressure vessel since strong deviations from the geodesic winding angle are clearly possible in the vicinity of the polar opening (Fig. 14).

The described effects result in a non-axisymmetric filament wound structure and can be accurately represented by the enhanced filament winding simulation presented here. The consequences of these differences on the results of the finite element analysis are being studied presently.

Fig. 14. Winding pattern and band overlap in the vicinity of the polar opening

Fig. 15. Number of bands at sampling points along one particular meridian path

Fig. 16. Dependence of the engineering modulus on the fiber angle for single-ply and symmetric angle-ply laminates of a typical carbon fiber reinforced epoxy material

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